

INTEGRATED TERRITORIAL PLANNING OF A HOMOGENEOUS MOUNTAIN SYSTEM. THE *CRAIULUI FOREST* MICROREGION

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Abstract

According to the scientific method that served as the foundation for its creation, the article suggests two different kinds of methods. The first strategy concentrates on theoretical and methodological elements with the goal of examining the primary facets of territorial planning from an integrated approach at the mountain area level. Applied to the current situation in Craiului Forest, the second strategy is pragmatic and considers the attainment of integrated territorial coherence as well as the reduction of social and economic disparities at the component locality level.

The specific objectives analyzed in the article are consistent with the trajectory of the logic of the scientific approach, as follows: (1) presenting the main elements of the integrated territorial planning process; (2) analyzing the economic and social profile of the mountain area; (3) conducting a SWOT analysis for each of the evaluated areas; (4) identifying the main objectives of the integrated development strategy and the directions of action at the level of the Craiului Forest (CF) mountain microregion.

The article represents the result of research carried out within CE_MONT in 2024, as part of the strategic program-CEM 1, entitled "*Mountain bioeconomy and renewable resources; Circular economy and social economy as factors for revitalizing disadvantaged mountain communities*". Within the framework of the aforementioned program, the study "*Feasibility analysis for a territorial development model of a mountain microregion, as a support for the application of knowledge-based bioeconomy. Application: Pădurea Craiului Bioarea*", coordinated by Ms. PhD economist Daniela Antonescu, was developed.

Keywords: *Craiului Forest (CF), territorial planning, integrated mountain development*

INTRODUCTION

The development planning of a mountain area aims to establish regulations regarding the use of the specific territory and the organization of human activities within it. The process has a transversal character, as it simultaneously involves multiple fields: geography, geology, architecture, economy, technical and engineering elements, etc. The objective of the territorial planning process is to ensure a logical, coherent and coordinated interaction between different human activities, in order to achieve a balanced and sustainable territorial development (Antonescu 2024).

Territorial planning also aims to analyze and regulate the processes of managing a territory, including the dynamics and evolution of phenomena at the local level. The main instrument of territorial planning is the local development strategy, a functional and integrated instrument that forms the basis for political decision-making, evaluating the effects that human actions can have on a territory (Antonescu, Popa 2014).

The local development strategy includes a set of analyses, evaluations, actions, measures and resources, aimed at developing a specific area, in our case, a mountainous region. It aims to confront and solve real problems, through choices and prioritizations, under the conditions of

limited financial resources and high development needs (Pușcașu 2005). The strategy has a participatory character, based on the awareness of uncertainties and the need to control certain future events. The fragile balance of coexistence between anthropogenic dynamics and the environment has become a subject of scientific interest, given its importance from a theoretical and practical point of view (Antonescu 2024).

The principles that inspire the modern theories of territorial planning follow the design lines in accordance with the principles of sustainable development and environmental protection, both in the frenetic expansion capable of causing irreversible transformations to natural systems, and in the attempt to improve the quality of life for present and future generations (Câdea, Bran, Cimpoeru 2006).

Planning the development of an area is a strategic element that underlies future development decisions. At the same time, planning the development of a mountainous area must take into account a series of characteristics that define both the unity and the way to approach the specific issues that characterize these types of territories (Ianoș 2001).

The proposed case study focuses on the *Craiului Forest* mountainous area. The analyzed territory presents homogeneous characteristics in terms of relief, climate, soils, demographics, tourism, economic, social and cultural environment. The bioarea subject to analysis represents a component of the Bihor County territory and includes the area of eight communes: Răbăgani, Pomezueu, Dobrești, Roșia, Căbești, Curățele, Budureasa and Pietroasa. The eight communes extend over a territory of 1,007.6 km² and have a total population of 21,820 inhabitants (year 2023), representing 3.58% of the total population of Bihor County and 0.11% of the population of Romania.

In order to establish the objectives and funding from national and European programs, the development strategy of the Pădurea Craiului mountainous area should aim to stimulate rural tourism activities, develop local products, support small farms and local farmers and create new jobs. The article aims to analyze the most recent statistical data and indicators present in the official statistics (NIS) and to bring to the forefront the current problems and development prospects of the *Craiului Forest* mountain area, taking into account the new trends present at both national and community level (European Commission 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development strategy of the mountainous area reflects the condition of the component localities across different fields of activity (social, economic, infrastructure, administrative, etc.) and, based on consultation actions with relevant stakeholders, proposes development directions and actions, along with the main sources of financing.

The strategy contributes to strengthening administrative capacity and developing strategic planning, ensuring an increase in the quality of the long-term administrative act (Tălânga 2015). In Romania, all localities, whether urban or rural (including mountainous ones), must align with the directions and perspectives of the National Sustainable Development Strategy 2030 (NSDS) (adopted in 2018), which proposes a global vision of the country's evolution in the medium and long term. Each development strategy for a complex mountainous system should be based on the following components, presented in Table 1.

Any mountain development strategy must comply with a series of general principles of application: the principle of sustainable development, equality of rights and opportunities,

participation, local autonomy, cooperation and partnership between different institutions, impartiality and transparency.

Table 1. Basic components of a mountainous development strategy

Component	Strategic questions	Elements of analysis
Current situation and dynamics	Where are we? Evolutions Local development capacities and their functionality (conditionalities, interactions, influences)?	Internal/external environment analysis Identification of problems SWOT analysis.
Strategic options	Where do we want to go?	Vision, objectives and development measures.
Implementation and monitoring	How do we get there? Resources	Intervention models, operational planning actions. Monitoring and evaluation. Reevaluation.

Source: own processing on NIS data.

The development strategy of a mountain area must take into account the specific characteristics of these territories, as follows:

- they have a natural setting of inestimable value and beauty;
- significant areas with forests, pastures and hayfields;
- they have an important agricultural potential in terms of land resources and traditions of cultivation and animal husbandry;
- the possibility of practicing agrotourism as a complementary activity to agriculture;
- they have an important tourist and cultural potential;
- a limited accessibility and difficult geographical conditions;
- depopulation trends, low birth rate, aging, poverty;
- a limited industrialization and extensive agriculture, high biodiversity, products with significant biological quality (mountain products);
- the presence of a private sector in agriculture, with a low level of association;
- inadequate infrastructure (water, sewage, heating);
- a large number of subsistence farms with small areas (2 ha);
- continuous degradation of pasture and hayfield areas;
- some mountain areas are declared less-favoured areas (LDAs).

We present, below, synthetically, the stages of implementing a development strategy for a mountainous area. The overall approach to a mountainous development strategy takes into account the logic of specific interventions, and takes into account the existence of certain premises: ensuring the commitment and consensus of the parties involved, appointing a manager or coordinator, ensuring partnerships, forming working groups, informing local communities.

RESEARCH METODOLOGY

The proposed methodology integrates elements of spatial analysis and planning, systems of general and specific indicators, contextual characteristics of the investigated area, and can be replicated in other categories of mountain areas.

The methodology for approaching the proposed objectives focuses on:

- An analytical plan designed to identify the evolution and trends of the main indicators grouped in different fields (demographics, economy, infrastructure, health, education, etc.),
- A conceptual and prospective plan – application of working methods that consisted of: documentary analysis, statistical data processing, graphic representations and analyses, analysis of the legislative framework, etc.

The data used comes from the Tempo on-line statistical indicator database (<http://statistici.insse.ro/shop/?page=tempo1> <=ro>). The analysis was applied to the eight UATs in the *Craiului Forest* bioarea (by centralizing the values of specific and general indicators from different fields); these UATs operate on the basis of Law 351/2001 on the approval of the National Territorial Development Plan - Section IV The Network of Localities. The subject of the analysis is the Pădurea Craiului bioarea, located in the southeastern part of Bihor County, up to the border with Alba County, and being part of the Beiuș depression.

The territory of *Craiului Forest* covers the area that includes eight communes: **Răbăgani, Pomezue, Dobrești, Roșia, Căbești, Curățele, Budureasa and Pietroasa**. This mountainous region maintains territorial continuity and shares common and homogeneous characteristics in terms of relief, climate, soils, demographics, tourism, economic, social and cultural environment extending over a total area of 1,007.55 km². The closest cities are Beiuș, Ștei and Oradea, with road access to Cluj and Alba counties (Map 1).

Fig. 1. Map 1 Craiului Forest bioarea

Source: https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mun%C8%9Bii_P%C4%83durea_Craiului#/media/Fi%C8%99ier:Apuseni_in_Romania.jpg

A large area of the bioarea's territory is a Natura 2000 protected area, rich in attractive and interesting objectives for mountain tourism. It is also an area rich in local traditions and crafts practiced since ancient times and preserved unaltered to this day. Like the entire rural area, the infrastructure and the economic sector require significant modernization interventions (Alexandrescu-Dersca, Bulgaru 1972).

The main stages of the methodology are:

1. Consulting the specialized literature (recent studies and strategic documents).
2. Identifying specific indicators and the main databases (Eurostat, INS, etc.).
3. Processing the indicators with the help of established statistical methods (dynamics, structures, etc.).
4. Analyses and syntheses on the websites of the responsible institutions.

5. Identifying new/recent examples of good practice, which can be multiplied with important positive effects.

RESULTS

Demography

The *Craiului Forest (CF)* mountainous area holds 3.58% of the population of Bihor County, marking a slight decrease compared to 2014 (3.73%). The demographic dynamics show a sharper decline in CF compared to the county (-5.69% compared to -1.85%).

According to NIS data, in 2023, the total population of the bioarea was 21,820 inhabitants, 5.69% less than in 2014. The trend indicates a constant decrease in the population of the mountainous territory, in the last 9 years, effectively losing 1,316 inhabitants.

The analyzed data revealed that there are two communes with under 2,000 inhabitants: Căbești with 1,723 inhabitants and Răbăgani with 1,946 inhabitants. The most populous locality is Dobrești, with 5,341 inhabitants, followed by Pietroasa with 3,014 inhabitants. The other communes are: Budureasa – 2,687 inhabitants, Curățele – 2,329 inhabitants, Roșia – 2,303 inhabitants, Pomezeu – 2,477 inhabitants (as of July 1, 2023) (table 2).

Table 2. Population (No. Hab.) (2014-2023)

Localities	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Dynamics (%)
Budureasa	2708	2701	2704	2716	2715	2701	2709	2731	2689	2687	-0,78
Căbești	1870	1856	1854	1836	1817	1807	1796	1766	1747	1723	-7,86
Curățele	2451	2446	2442	2447	2439	2414	2400	2363	2351	2329	-4,98
Dobrești	5454	5442	5450	5447	5444	5401	5398	5362	5319	5341	-2,07
Pietroasa	3244	3208	3183	3167	3136	3124	3080	3052	3032	3014	-7,09
Răbăgani	2037	2024	1991	1984	1978	1970	1964	1958	1933	1946	-4,47
Roșia	2488	2453	2466	2458	2447	2421	2404	2367	2324	2303	-7,44
Pomezeu	2884	2819	2774	2722	2.700	2653	2620	2559	2507	2477	-14,11
Total	23.136	22.949	22.864	22.777	22.676	22.491	22.371	22.158	21.902	21.820	-5,69

Source: own processing, NIS data.

The evolution of the total population by locality shows a downward trend in all component localities. The largest decrease in the number of inhabitants, in 2023, was registered in Pomezeu (-14.11%), followed by Căbești (-7.86%) and Pietroasa (-7.09%). The smallest demographic decrease, in the period 2014-2023, was recorded in Budureasa (-0.78%) (National Institute of Statistics).

In *Craiului Forest*, in 2023, there were 10,947 men and 10,752 women (49.6% are women and 50.4% are men). In 2014, out of a the total of 23,231 inhabitants, about 50.02% were women and 49.08% were men. During the analyzed period, a slight reversal of the percentages is observed, with men becoming slightly the majority (National Institute of Statistics).

The dynamics of the preschool population shows a negative trend in six out of the eight localities. The largest decreases are reported in Pomezeu (-23.81%) and Căbești (-23.4%). The only localities that recorded an increase in the preschool population are Dobrești (+14.22%) and Răbăgani (+12.28%). Overall, the bioarea records a decrease in the preschool population of -3.64%.

The analysis by age group shows that there are significant increases in the male population in the age group 50-54 (+54%), this being the so-called baby boom generation (1968-1970) and in the population over 85 (+23%). The largest decreases are in the age groups 40-44 (-22.64%), 60-64 (-17.25%) and 80-84 (-23.67%). For the female population, the largest increases are in the category 50-54 (+53.58%), followed by those over 85 years (+35%), 70-74 (+12.58%) and 45-49 (+8.98%). The largest decreases occur in the 60-64 age category (-32%), 80-84 age category (-19.9%) and 35-39 age category (-20.59%) (National Institute of Statistics).

The demographic aging index (calculated by comparing people over 65 years old to those under 14 years old) has increased for both men and women. A more pronounced aging process is observed among the female population compared to the male population. Among men, the aging index rose from 92.96% to 99.78%, while for women, it increased from 128.05% to 153.03%, showing a clear aging process.

Two relevant demographic indicators are further analyzed, in order to outline the overall demographic picture of the Craiului Forest bioarea: people aged 0-14 and people over 65. Thus, in the two years analyzed 2014 and 2023, there is an obvious trend of reduction of the population under 14 years old (from 16.91% to 13.25%). As for the population over 65 years old, it records a significant growth trend, from 20.5% to 22.26%.

In 2023, the number of live births was 204, with 3.8% fewer than in 2014. One aspect that can be commented on here is the fact that in 2020, the year of the pandemic, the most children were born, 263, being a peak value of the indicator. After the lifting of restrictions, in 2021, the value of the indicator decreased by 17.9%, and in 2022, the decline was more moderate compared to 2020 (8.7%). The year 2023 recorded the lowest value of the indicator in the Craiului Forest mountainous area, with 204 live newborns, representing a decrease of -22.4%, compared to the pandemic year 2020.

Another relevant indicator is the number of deceased persons, which, in 2023, in the analyzed area was of 304 persons, 15.3% less than in 2014 (359 deceased). By locality, the most deceased persons were reported in Răbăgani (+21.4%) and Roșia (+17.9%). Decreases in the number of deaths were in Dobrești (-40%), Pomezueu (-37.3%), Budureasa (-10.5%) and Căbești (-7.9%).

Regarding the natural increase (number of live births - deceased), in the CF area 204 children were born and 304 people died, so there was a negative increase of 100 people. The analysis by locality shows that the only locality where a positive natural increase was recorded is Dobrești (+14 people). The other localities reported negative values, the highest value being in Curățete (-30), followed by Căbești (-27 people), Pietroasa (-19 people) and Roșia (-18 people). The number of marriages was 139, 20.9% more than in 2014. By locality, the most marriages were registered in Pietroasa (+78.6%), followed by Pomezueu (+72.7%) and Dobrești (+52.2%).

Also, in the period 2014-2023, there was an increase in the number of settlements from 89 people to 95 people (+6.7%), but also an increase in the number of departures (+15%), from 253 people to 291 people. It is noted that the number of departures exceeds that of arrivals. During the health crisis, an increase in the number of settlements in the bioarea localities (+486.52%) was observed, after which their number decreased significantly.

A hierarchy of the TAUs (Territorial Administrativ Units) in the Craiului Forest bioarea was created according to the values of the analyzed indicators, as follows (year 2023) (table 3).

Table 3. Place of the TAUs in the *Craiului Forest* bioarea, according to the analyzed demographic indicators, 2023

Localities	Population	Population growth	Female	Female growth	Live births (dynamics)	Deaths (dynamics)	Settlements (dynamics)	Departures	Marriages	Divorces	Natural increase	Preschool population (dynamics)
Budureasa	3	1	3	1	6	6	2	2	6	2	2	6
Căbești	8	4	8	7	7	5	5	7	7	3	7	8
Curățele	5	6	5	3	8	3	4	8	4	4	8	2
Dobrești	1	2	1	2	3	8	6	4	3	5	1	1
Pietroasa	2	5	2	6	4	4	7	1	1	-	6	5
Pomezueu	4	8	4	8	2	7	1	3	2	1	3	7
Răbăgani	7	3	7	4	1	1	8	6	5	4	4	3
ROȘIA	6	7	6	5	5	2	3	5	8	2	5	4

Sources: own computation on NIS data.

Table 4 presents the SWOT analysis based on the analyzed indicators.

Table 4. SWOT Analysis - Demography

STRONG POINTS	WEAK POINTS
<p>Increase in male population. In Budureasa, there is an increase in the male population of 0.67%, and the smallest decrease in the female population, of only -1.47%. The largest male population is in Dobrești (24.3%), followed by Pietroasa (14%) and Budureasa (12.5%) (year 2023). Increase in the preschool population: Dobrești (+14.22%) and Răbăgani (+12.28%). Slight trend of increase in the number of preschoolers. Increase in the preschool population for both men and women (33.06%, respectively 28.7%) Reduction in deaths (-15.3%). Increase in the number of marriages (+29.9%).</p>	<p>Population reduction by 5.69%. All TAUs recorded negative demographic dynamics. Higher demographic decrease compared to the county level. Decrease in the importance of the population in the county context. The female population is experiencing a slight growth trend. Almost all ATUs recorded decreases in both gender groups (except Budureasa). Decrease in the preschool population by -3.64%; the largest decreases in Pomezueu (-23.81%) and Căbești (-23.4%). Dramatic decrease in men in the 0-14 age category (-41.89%). In women, the dramatic decrease occurs in the 44-64 age category (-23.2%), followed by the 35-44 age category (-18.2%). Increase in the male population over 85 years old by +23% and in the female population over 85 years old by +35%. Decreases in the male population are reported in the age groups 40-44 years old (-22.64%), 60-64 years old (-17.25%) and 80-84 years old (-23.67%). The aging index increased from 92.96% to 99.78% in the male population, and in the female population an increase from 128.05% to 153.03%. Reduction in the population under 14 years old (from 16.91% to 13.25%). The population over 65 years old increases, from 20.5% to 22.26%. The number of live births is 3.8% less in 2023 than in 2014. Negative natural growth. Increasing trend in the number of divorces (+38.5%). The number of departures is higher than the number of settlements.</p>
OPORTUNITIES	RISKS
<p>The life of country wide packages that help households to be able to grow the birth rate. Increasing the elegance of the area to keep its appeal to the population. Increasing the pleasant nature of lifestyles of the population. European budget and PNRR. National packages for the development of social housing for younger people. Involving nearby public government in solving social problems.</p>	<p>Depopulation of some localities as a result of negative natural increase, departures with residence, population aging. Increase in the demographic dependency ratio. Population aging.</p>

Health

In the *Craiului Forest* mountain area, 18 family doctors work in the private health system, most of them in the Roșia locality. The number of doctors remained constant during the analyzed period).

Regarding the average health personnel, it was 27 (in 2022), increasing compared to 2014 with one medical staff from the public health system. There are 9 dentists and 10 pharmacists.

In order to reveal the population's access to doctors in the public sector, we reported the population of the *Craiului Forest* bioarea to the number of doctors, in 2014 and 2022. Regarding the number of inhabitants per private sector doctor (per 1,000 inhabitants), it was one doctor per 1,212 inhabitants (5.7% more than in 2014). One healthcare professional with secondary education is responsible for 808 inhabitants, down 9.2% less than in 2014.

The number of cardiovascular patients in the Craiului Forest area increased from 2,846 people to 5,434 people, with a dynamics of 91%. By locality, most are reported in Dobrești, Pomezou, Curățele, etc. Compared to the total population, the number of cardiovascular patients increased from 12.72% to 24.9%, during the period 2020-2023.

In the mountainous area of Craiului Forest there is no medical unit, only individual family doctor's offices. There are permanent centers of family doctors in: Dobrești, Pomezou and Răbăgani.

Table 5 presents the SWOT analysis based on the analyzed indicators.

Table 5. SWOT Analysis – Health field

STRONG POINTS	WEAK POINTS
The private medical-sanitary sector is the basic sector in the Pădurea Craiului mountain area.	Relatively large number of inhabitants who return to a doctor. Lack of dental offices in some TAUs (Budureasa). Lack of involvement of the public health system in providing medical services in the mountainous area. Only three of the eight TAUs provide medical permanence services through family doctors. Very large population that returns to a family doctor or an average health worker. Population with serious health problems (cardiovascular diseases represent 24.9% of the total population).
OPORTUNITIES	RISKS
Financing possibilities from community and national grants for the rehabilitation of damaged buildings, or for the purchase of medical equipment and devices (RRNP, ROP North West, Horizon Europe programs). Possibility of improving the health status of the population as a result of the effects of the transition to a green economy.	The aging population, at high risk for the incidence and prevalence of various diseases, will put pressure on the public health system. Moreover, access to doctors and treatment options for chronic diseases are greatly reduced. In some localities with an aging population, access to treatment is hindered by the fact that medical facilities are poorly represented (some do not have family or dental practices). The disappearance of some categories of public facilities such as family, specialty or dental practices, along with the increase in private facilities.

Education

According to the INS, the total school population in the Craiului Forest area was 2,515 students in 2023, 15.05% fewer than in 2014. The trend of the school population was of continuous decrease, with a slight increase in 2021, possibly as a result of the return to the area of migrants who had gone to work abroad.

The largest school population is identified in pre-university education (77.14%). Within this, the most numerous are in primary education (48.6%), followed by those in middle school (39.07%) (table 6). In vocational education, the school population represents 5.31% of the pre-university one. The registered trends are those of decrease,

with the exception of vocational education which begins to gain ground, especially after 2020.

Table 6. School population between 2014 and 2022 (no.)

	2014	2020	2021	2023	2023 (%) Structure	Dynamics
School population (total)	2926	2536	2554	2515	-	-14.0
Children in kindergartens	721	579	579	575	22.86	-20.2
Pre-university	2205	1957	1975	1940	77.14	-12.0
Primary	1113	1005	992	944	48,66	-15.2
Gymnasium	912	758	795	758	39,07	-16.9
High school	180	102	109	135	6,96	-25.0
Vocational	:	92	79	103	5,31	

Sources: own computation on NIS data.

In the context of the research conducted, in the period 2014-2023, in the Craiului Forest bioarea there is a decrease in the total number of teaching positions in public education.

215 teachers are active in public education units (year 2023), -9.7% less than in 2014 (238 people). At the level of the TAUs, negative dynamics of teaching staff were recorded in almost all TAUs, except for the locality of Dobrești, where an increase of 3.8% was reported and in Curățele where the number remained constant throughout the period. The structural analysis shows that the locality of Dobrești has the largest number of teaching staff (38.1% of the total), followed at a great distance by Pietroasa (11.6%) and Budureasa (11.2%).

By category of education forms, the middle school predominates, which holds about 30.2% of the total in terms of teachers, followed by the high school (29.3%). The fewest teachers are found in preschool education, which holds 16.7% of the total. The dynamics over time are negative in almost all categories, except for high school education, which has a growth trend of 28.6%. The largest decrease is reported in primary education (-27.1%).

Compared to the number of school population, one teacher is responsible for 11.7 students (down from 2014, when there were 12.29 students per teacher). The average number of students per teacher in primary, secondary or lower secondary education in the European Union was 12.3 students (2020), with the highest ratio being in the Netherlands (16.5 students per teacher), France (14.9) and Romania (14.3 students per teacher).

At the opposite end of the scale, in Luxembourg there are 7.1 students per teacher, while in Greece there are 8.5 students per teacher, and in Malta 8.8 students per teacher.

The total number of graduates in the CF mountain area in 2022 was 241 schoolchildren, of which 81.3% were students enrolled in primary and secondary education (including special education), followed by high school (9.96%) and vocational education (8.71%). In 2022, the total school population was 2,531 people. If we report the number of graduates to the total school population, the result is a graduation rate of 10%.

There are 152 classrooms registered in the education system, 13.1% fewer than in 2014. The analysis of the structure shows that the most classrooms are found in Dobrești (38.2%), followed at a great distance by Pietroasa (13.8%) and Budureasa (10.5%). The development of the educational infrastructure in the mountain area suffered during the

period 2014-2023, this aspect being reflected in the reduction in the number of classrooms in all UATs, except for Dobrești (the number of classrooms increased by 5.5%).

Table 7 presents the SWOT analysis based on the analyzed indicators.

Table 7. SWOT Analysis - Education

STRONG POINTS	WEAK POINTS
<p>Each locality has an educational unit. Increase in the school population in post-secondary education. Trend of increasing importance of the population in high school and vocational education. Increase in the number of sports fields and IT equipment.</p>	<p>Negative dynamics of the school population (-15.05%). The reduction of teaching staff at the bioarea level (-9.7%). The school infrastructure shows a tendency to decrease (decrease in the number of classrooms, laboratories, workshops). Very low level of the total school population that is classified as a graduate (10%).</p>
OPORTUNITIES	RISKS
<p>The upward dynamics of post-secondary education will gradually satisfy part of the demand for qualified workers on the labor market. Possibility of obtaining non-reimbursable funding for education/human capital through the ROP North West, Resilient and Recovery National Plan, another programs.</p>	<p>The persistence of social problems will negatively affect school enrollment. The lack of involvement of families in facilitating the child's independent work and training; The poor remuneration of teaching staff in pre-university education. The decrease in the interest of adolescents in university studies, in school. The lack of prospects on the labor market - amplified by the current context, negatively influences the interest of young people in theoretical high schools and post-secondary schools.</p>

Agriculture

At the bioarea level, the land fund is distributed as follows by TAUs: the largest area is owned by the locality of Budureasa (34.25%), followed by Pietroasa (20.30%) and Dobrești (13.29%). The smallest area is registered in Răbăgani (3.5%).

Regarding private property, at the level of the Craiului Forest bioarea there is an extremely different situation from one TAU to another. Overall, private property owns 61.52% of the area, but by TAUs this differs from a maximum of 89.1% in Pomezueu, 86.4% in Răbăgani and a minimum of 38.7% in Pietroasa. The analysis of the land fund by the component TAUs is presented below:

- The largest agricultural area is found in the locality of Budureasa (28.04%), followed by Dobrești (12.72%); the smallest agricultural area is in Răbăgani (7.72%).
- In terms of arable land, Dobrești ranks first, with a percentage of 18.33% of the total, followed by Pomezueu (15.95%) and Răbăgani (14.22%).
- In forests, the largest areas are found in Budureasa (44.79%), followed by Pietroasa (10.54%) and Curățele (10.45%).
- In Budureasa, we find 1 hectare of vineyards and wine-growing areas.
- In hayfields, the first place is held by Roșia (27.4%), followed by Pietroasa (20.47%) and Căbești (12.72%).
- Budureasa holds 65.63% of the area of water and ponds.
- About 51% of the area covered by railways is also found in Budureasa.
- Degraded lands are in Pietroasa (27.12% of the area of degraded lands).

- 54,697 ha. area covered with forests, with a degree of coverage that varies from a maximum of 37.34% in Budureasa, to a minimum of 0.53% in Răbăgani.
- The main areas are those cultivated with corn grains (4,144 hectares), wheat and rye (2,752 ha.), potatoes (1,000 ha.), vegetables (418 ha).

At the level of the Craiului Forest area, the Association LOCAL ACTION GROUP *CRAIULUI FOREST* (LAG) operates, which coordinates the relevant interest groups in the territory. Economic and social partners, as well as other representatives of civil society, represent 64.44% of the local partnership. The LAG territory includes 26 partners, as follows: 8 TAUs, the communes: Roșia, Răbăgani, Dobrești, Căbești, Curatele, Pomezueu, Pietroasa, Budureasa; 5 SRL (limited liability companies), 5 PFA (authorized natural persons), 1 family business, 6 ONG (non-governmental organizations), of which two from outside the LAG area, 1 relevant natural person (Lascu Viorel).

The Center for Protected Areas and Sustainable Development – Bihor is an important NGO, established on the basis of a partnership between two institutions and two NGOs: Bihor County Council, the Faculty of Environmental Protection of Oradea, the Romanian Speleology Federation and the Regional Center for Ecological Surveillance “Apuseni Mountains”. CAPDD Bihor is a member of the Natura 2000 network, the Ecotourism Association of Romania (AER), the Advisory Council for the Management of the Apuseni Natural Park, the Romanian Speleology Federation and a partner of the Leave No Trace network in the USA. Since February 2010, CAPDD Bihor has held the custody of the Natura 2000 site ROSCI 0062 “Defileul Crișului Repede – Pădurea Craiului”.

In the analyzed mountainous area, there are three TAUs that have certified mountain products: Budureasa (fresh mushrooms), Curățele (rosehip jam, onion) and Pomezueu (Fam. acacia honey).

Another product that the mountain area offers for processing and valorization is the clay extracted from the Pădurea Craiului Mountains. The company that valorizes it is Farmec, the largest Romanian cosmetics manufacturer, and the first local company to use natural clay from the Craiului FOREST Mountains in its own production. For over 17 years, this ingredient has been the basis for the development of the *Aslavital Mineralactiv* range.

Table 8 presents the SWOT analysis based on the analyzed indicators.

Table 8. SWOT Analysis - Agriculture

STRONG POINTS	WEAK POINTS
<p>Large area of agricultural land (487 thousand ha.). Relatively large arable land (309 thousand ha. 63.45%). Large areas with forests (26.29% of the land fund). Large areas of pastures favorable for animal husbandry (pastures represent 17.36% of it). Significant private property (75.66%). Culinary and craft traditions preserved unaltered.</p>	<p>Semi-subsistence agriculture. Reluctance to form associations at the local level and low associative spirit. Agricultural areas left uncultivated. Reduction of areas cultivated with vegetables. Reduced capacity for processing and valorization of plant and livestock products. Handicrafts and crafts activities on the verge of extinction. There is no agricultural production cooperative. Lack of participation and market orientation of farms. Products declared as mountain products in small numbers compared to local possibilities. Lack of Local Gastronomic Points.</p>

OPORTUNITIES	RISKS
<p>The presence of the Craiului Forest LAG, which can support and promote viable partnerships at the level of mountain farms, can help farmers access community or national funds to support agricultural activities.</p> <p>Important natural potential for the development of agriculture.</p> <p>Possibilities for rapid growth of areas intended for organic agriculture.</p> <p>Programs aimed at developing and consolidating organic agriculture and animal husbandry.</p> <p>Supporting small mountain farmers through various agricultural support measures.</p> <p>Diversifying activities in mountain localities.</p> <p>Preserving and promoting traditions related to animal husbandry.</p> <p>Programs that can finance the protection of the forest fund.</p> <p>Developing activities for processing and marketing wood products.</p> <p>Possibilities for hunting and obtaining additional sources of income from hunting.</p> <p>Developing the sector that capitalizes on berries and mushrooms.</p> <p>Additional sources of income from the capitalization of forest products.</p> <p>Programs to support fruit growing activities.</p> <p>NPRD 2021-2027, LEADER Program.</p> <p>The interest of local authorities to support small mountain producers and to try to attract young people to this area.</p>	<p>Maintaining the practice of subsistence agriculture.</p> <p>Difficulty in entering the market with small quantities of agricultural products.</p> <p>Strict and costly legal framework for registering traditional products under the local/regional origin mark.</p> <p>Failure to meet deadlines in starting and carrying out rural development projects.</p> <p>Poor processing of agri-food products.</p> <p>Low competitiveness of mountain farms.</p>

Tourism and the promotion of cultural heritage

The Craiului Forest Mountains have an area of about 1,150 km² and are administratively located in the central-eastern part of Bihor County, occupying 15.2% of the total area. At the same time, they represent the closest mountain area to the city of Oradea, being located about 35 km. from Vârciorog and 60 km from Șuncuiuș.

The geography of the Craiului Forest Mountains is characterized by slightly prominent ridges, which often spread into large karst plateaus. It is an unconventional relief, which presents poorly individualized ridges, oriented in almost all directions. The features are specific to the central and northeastern areas of Craiului Forest (about 80% of the massif's surface) (Ciangă, Deszi 2007).

Specialists in the field say that Craiului Forest presents the most diverse offer of nature experiences in Romania. The mountain area is located in a protected area and has the largest number of tour operators and adventure activity organizers in Bihor County, being a perfect tourist destination for adrenaline junkies, mountain lovers, bike riders or those who want to relax in the fresh air.

1. *Mountain tourism* - the most practiced form of tourism is mountain hiking. The area is a true hiking paradise, here you can practice routes for different categories of tourists (beginners, advanced), trekking on rocks and marked paths. The main hiking routes are: "Peștera" Vadu Crișului Cabin – Peștera Bătrânului, Valea Boiului Circuit,

Yellow Circuit of the Crişului Repede Gorge, “Peştera Vadu Crişului Cabin” – Valea Mişidului – Peştera Moanei, “Peştera Vadu Crişului Cabin” – Şunciuş.

Cycling (on the Crişului Repede Valley, on the Roşie Valley, on the Iadului Valley, etc.)

2. *Via ferrata routes:*

- Via ferrata route – “La Pendul”
- Via ferrata route – “Podul Indian”
- Via ferrata route – “Peretele Zânelor”
- Via ferrata route – “Montana Piticot”
- Via ferrata route – “Grota cu hamace”
- Via ferrata route – “Casa Zmeului”

3. *Rafting*

Rafting on the Crişului Repede river is intended for those who love mountain sports, with and without experience. Descent on rapid waters requires coordination and teamwork, which is why it is becoming increasingly popular with families, groups of friends, but also for team building activities.

4. “Caii Liberi” in Craiului Forest – a sports club that offers Western-style riding activities to enthusiasts, by frequently organizing camps for children or adults.

5. *Edu-venture in Craiului Forest* – a didactic project arranged in protected natural areas, on special thematic trails and with important value in educating the younger generations. The lessons are interactive and transformative, offering useful and interesting information about the forest, its creatures, the geological and mining past of the inhabitants.

6. *Thematic trails:*

- “Discover Valea Roşia”
- “Without a trace”
- “Animals in the forest”
- “Racul Bihorean” trail,

7. Cheile Cuţii - here are the last areas with forested karst in Europe (Roşia). The great diversity of plant and animal species suggests an area where human activities do not yet have a significant negative impact, therefore, in order to protect the area, the principle “Visit the Cut Gorges responsibly” must be applied.

8. *Padiş* – Padiş tourist area - located in the northern branch of the Bihor Mountains, the Padiş area is located within the Pietroasa commune (up to the border with Cluj and Alba counties).

9. *Stâna de Vale* - is located at an altitude of 1,102 m. Stâna de Vale looks like a suspended basin with altitudes of about 1,100 - 1,200 m. From Stâna de Vale you can take the picturesque road, 42 km long, on the Valea Iadului where the Leş reservoir is also located. In the vicinity of Chişcau is the Bears' Cave. Known as one of the most spectacular tourist attractions of the Apuseni Mountains, the Bears' Cave is located near the town of Chişcau, Pietroasa Commune, Bihor County, at an altitude of 482 meters. Here, it was the shelter of bears 15,000 years ago. Due to the fall of a rock, the mouth of the cave was blocked, and over 140 bears remained stuck inside (starving, they attacked each other until they all died).

Tourist infrastructure

As shown in Table 9, the number of these tourist reception structures has increased steadily during the period 2014-2024, from 10 to 42 (+300%). The increase in the number of tourist structures in Craiului Forest was higher than the increase recorded in Bihor County (+263.8%).

The most tourist reception structures were reported in Pietroasa (20 units), followed by Budureasa (13 units), Roşia (7 units) and Curăţele (2 units). The other four TAUs did not register any units with tourist functions. The highest dynamics are recorded in Pietroasa (400%), followed by Budureasa (160%) and Curăţele (100%).

Table 9. Tourist reception structures in the Pădurea Craiului mountain area, 2014 and 2024 (no., %)

Total	Counties	2014 (no.)	2024 (no.)	2024 vs. 2014 Dynamics (%)
-	Bihor	149	542	263.8
-	Budureasa	5	13	160.0
-	Curăţele	1	2	100.0
-	Pietroasa	4	20	400.0
-	Roşia	...	7	...
		10	42	320
CF in total county Bihor (%)		6,71	7,75	7,75

Source: own computation on NIS data.

In the Craiului Forest mountain area, there is only one hotel operating, located in Budureasa, while in Bihor County there are 54 hotels in operation (with an increase of 31.7% in 2024 compared to 2014). In the mountainous area, there are 14 apartments and rooms for rent, in Budureasa (4 tourist structures) and Pietroasa (10 tourist structures).

The mountainous area accounts for 2.60% of the county's total arrivals, up from 1.13% in 2014. The dynamics of the indicator show that, in 2023 compared to 2014, there was a significant increase in arrivals in the mountainous area (+131.2%). The largest increases in tourist arrivals were reported in Roşia (+801%), Pietroasa (+701.1%) and Budureasa (+260.2%). Arrivals in apartments and rooms for rent reached 5,103 people, while in tourist villas the number of people was 1,428 (an increase of 212.5%). In agro-tourism guesthouses, 2,801 people arrived (+887%) (table 10).

Table 10. Tourist arrivals in tourist reception structures by type of structure, in Bihor County and in the localities of Craiului Forest, 2014 and 2024 (no. of persons, %)

Total	Counties	2014	2023	Dynamics
Total	Bihor	298,275	584,249	95.9
-	Budureasa	2,404	8,659	260.2
-	Curăţele	201	317	57.7
-	Pietroasa	558	4,470	701.1
-	Roşia	196	1,766	801.0
Total CF		3,359	15,212	352.9
% in the county		1.13	2.60	131.2
Hotels	Bihor	224,411	405,197	80.6
-	Budureasa	1,947	4,005	105.7

	Counties	2014	2023	Dynamics
Apartments and rented rooms	Bihor	:	42,831	
-	Budureasa	:	2,173	
-	Pietroasa	:	2,930	
Total CF			5,103	
Touristic villas	Bihor	5,844	23,588	303.6
-	Budureasa	457	1,428	212.5
-	Curățele	201	0	-100.0
Total CF		658	1,428	112.47
Tourist cabins	Bihor	456	2,083	356.8
-	Pietroasa	:	505	
Agro-tourism guesthouses	Bihor	31,394	81,248	158.8
-	Budureasa	:	1,053	
-	Curățele	:	317	
-	Pietroasa	558	1,035	85.5
-	Roșia	196	1,766	801.0
Total CF		754	2,801	886.5

Source: own computation on NIS data.

It is noted that tourist arrivals have fluctuated from one year to another, with a clear upward trend. Thus, if in Budureasa, the ratio was 1.59 tourists per inhabitant in 2019, it subsequently increased to 3.22 (2023). In Curățele, this ratio decreased from 0.21 to 0.14, while in Pietroasa it increased from 0.74 to 1.48. The locality of Roșia also registered a downward trend, from 1.1 to 0.77. Table 11 presents the SWOT analysis based on the analyzed indicators.

Table 11. SWOT Analysis – Tourism

STRONG POINTS	WEAK POINTS
Existence of protected natural areas. Diversity of the natural environment. Practice of various forms of tourism. Variety of cultural heritage. A turistic resorts or areas equipped with cable infrastructure for winter sports (Stâna de Vale). The number of tourist reception structures has increased constantly. Significant increase in arrivals.	There is only one hotel operating in CF. Reduced number of tourist reception structures. Overnight stays have been reduced by more than half.
OPORTUNITIES	RISKS
Increased interest of visitors. Some programme for the development/implementation of cultural routes. Interest in the development of specific tourist infrastructure, Development of information and communication technology in the tourism field. Interest in concluding thematic partnerships. Existence of European funds and national programs.	Climate and anthropogenic changes. Fragmentation of holidays. A high degree of protection/conservation for natural parks. Competition from other tourist destinations. Lack of qualified labor. Loss of funds from various national or community programs. A few integrated development strategies in the mountain area.

Workforce and antreprenorial sector

The analysis was carried out based on the official age groups to be able to enter the labor market. In 2023, 12,572 people were registered in the age category of labor resources 20-64 years, 5.6% less compared to 2014. Continuing this negative dynamics, in the coming period, labor resources will no longer be able to be restored to the same level nor will they be able to provide the labor market with appropriate resources, thus identifying a significant deficit in this sector.

Overall, male labor resources recorded a decrease of -3.06%, while the female population decreased by -8.26% (table 12).

Table 12. Dynamics of labor resources in the CF mountain area, by age categories and gender groups (no. Hab., %)

Age group	Male	Male	Dynamics	Female	Female	Dynamics
	2014	2023	2023 vs. 2014 (%)	2014	2023	2023 vs. 2014 (%)
20-24	793	720	-9.21	736	605	-17.80
25-29	839	728	-13.23	645	644	-0.16
30-34	736	740	0.54	703	608	-13.51
35-39	928	765	-17.56	748	594	-20.59
40-44	923	714	-22.64	824	692	-16.02
45-49	771	904	17.25	668	728	8.98
50-54	581	895	54.04	530	814	53.58
55-59	707	709	0.28	773	663	-14.23
60-64	626	518	-17.25	781	531	-32.01
Total	6,904	6,693	-3.06	6,408	5,879	-8.26

Source: own computation on NIS data.

One aspect considered a weak point is the gross registered activity rate (or general activity rate). This gross activity rate was, in 2023, 57.62%, slightly increasing compared to 2014, when it was 57.54% (+0.08%). The analysis of the existing workforce (number of employees) shows that, in 2022, it was 1,988 employees, increasing compared to 2019, by 10.69% (in 2019 there were 1,796 employees). The evolution of the indicator is relatively similar across the eight TAUs, consisting of a relative increase of approximately 10-11%. By structure, the relative number of employees is approximately 250 employees per TAU (table 13).

Table 13. Average number of employees, 2019-2022 (no., %)

TAUs	2019	2020	2021	2022	Dynamics	Structure
Budureasa	221	229	237	245	10.86	12.32
Căbești	222	230	238	246	10.81	12.37
Curățele	223	231	239	247	10.76	12.42
Drăgănești	224	232	240	248	10.71	12.47
Pietroasa	225	233	241	249	10.67	12.53
Pomezueu	226	234	242	250	10.62	12.58
Răbăgani	227	235	243	251	10.57	12.63
Roșia	228	236	244	252	10.53	12.68
Total	1,796	1,860	1,924	1,988	10.69	100.00

Sources: own computation on NIS data.

Regarding unemployment, at the bioarea level, 444 unemployed people were registered (November 2024), up 150.8% compared to November 2021. By locality, the most unemployed people are registered in Budureasa (174 unemployed; 30.2%), followed by Răbăgani, Dobrești and Pietroasa (each with 11%). Unemployed men number 245, representing 55.2% of the total, up from 85 people (2021, November) (+182%). Unemployed women were 199 people in November 2024, up from 92 people in November 2021 (+116%). The most unemployed are in Budureasa (108). Unemployed women are 199, up from 92 (+116.3%). Most unemployed women are Budureasa. The economic-entrepreneurial profile of the localities in the Craiului Forest bioarea is analyzed using the indicators Turnover per employee and Natural growth of enterprises. Turnover is defined as the total value of products and services provided by a company, over a determined period of time. It consists of the revenues that the company achieves as a result of the activity carried out in a financial year. The economic profile of the Craiului Forest mountain area (top 5 profitable activities) is presented in the following table.

Table 14. Economic profile of CF (Top activities after turnover/employee)

Communes	Activities
Budureasa	Restaurants and food services, Veterinary activities, Land transport, Wood processing, wood products, Building construction.
Căbești	Food industry, Wholesale trade, Metal construction industry, Agriculture, Forestry and logging.
Dobrești	Building construction, Metal construction, Civil engineering work, Food industry, Tanning, leather finishing.
Curățele	Secretarial activities, support services, Wholesale trade, Wood processing, Building construction, Waste treatment.
Pietroasa	Wholesale trade, Land and pipeline transport, Machinery and equipment manufacturing, Forestry and logging, Building construction
Pomezueu	Forestry and logging, Land and pipeline transport, Wholesale and retail trade, Warehousing and auxiliary transport activities, Special construction work.
Răbăgani	Civil engineering, Retail trade, Land and pipeline transport, Repair, maintenance and installation of machinery and equipment, Metal construction industry.
Roșia	Sports and recreation activities, Land and pipeline transport, Restaurants, Fishing and aquaculture, Wholesale trade.

Source: own computation on NIS data.

Romania ranks last in the European Union -27 in terms of SME density, with 2.71 million employees employed in around 426,000 small and medium-sized companies. Furthermore, it ranks 17th in the European Union in terms of total value added of small and medium-sized companies.

In Romania, there are 21.3 small and medium-sized companies/1000 inhabitants, the EU average being 42.7 companies. The highest densities are in the Czech Republic, with 95.9 SMEs per thousand inhabitants, Portugal (73.5 SMEs/1,000 inhabitants), Malta (73 SMEs/1,000 inhabitants) and Slovakia (70.2 SMEs/1,000 inhabitants).

In the mountainous area of Craiului Forest, the density of active companies ranges from 14.89 companies/1000 inhabitants. to 21.44 companies/1000 inhabitants (year 2022). In most localities, an increase in the density of active companies per 1000 inhabitants is observed. Table 15 presents the SWOT analysis based on the analyzed indicators.

Table 15. SWOT Analysis – Workforce/economic development

STRONG POINTS	WEAK POINTS
<p>Gross activity rate slightly increasing.</p> <p>Average increase in the number of employees.</p> <p>Increases in entrepreneurial capacity in seven out of eight TAUs.</p> <p>All communes increased their density of active firms per 1000 inhabitants.</p>	<p>Reduction of labor resources</p> <p>Relatively aging labor resources</p> <p>High share of the age group over 50 years</p> <p>Significant decreases in the male group at 40-44 years</p> <p>In the female group, significant decreases at: 60-64 years, 35-39 years, 20-24 years.</p> <p>Male labor resources recorded a decrease of -3.06%, while the female population decreased by -8.26%.</p> <p>The economic profile is given by: trade, forestry and animal husbandry, construction, transport, restaurant, recreational activities, logging (sectors with low added value).</p> <p>Negative natural growth of firms.</p> <p>Five of the eight communes have not developed Local Development Strategies for the period 2021-2027.</p>
OPORTUNITIES	RISKS
<p>Important sources of financing (ROP, another program).</p> <p>Increased demand for some tourist services specific to the area.</p> <p>Means of promotion on the national, European and international market.</p> <p>Organization of national and international tourism fairs.</p> <p>Existence of certification systems for ecotourism and agrotourism guesthouses (ANTREC, ECO-ROMÂNIA).</p>	<p>Regional and national competition and multiple crises, including recent global changes.</p> <p>Legislative instability in the field.</p> <p>Difficult lending to the tourism business sector.</p> <p>Lack of predictability of the legislative framework for business.</p> <p>Lack of financial resources for small producers (SMEs) for production diversification and higher technology.</p>

Utility Infrastructure (Potable Water, Energy, Gas)

Simple potable water distribution network

In the Craiului Forest mountainous area, the length of the potable water distribution network is 280.8 km, representing a 43.4% increase compared to 2014. An analysis by locality shows that the largest potable water network is in Dobrești (26.65% of the total), followed by Răbăgani (14.58%) and Pomezueu (13.29%).

Regarding the dynamics, there was a remarkable increase in the potable water network in Dobrești (from 1.5 km to 74.4 km), followed by Roșia (+52.9%) and Pomezueu (+41.6%). In Răbăgani and Pietroasa, the situation in 2023 was similar to that in 2014, while Căbești recorded a reduction in network length by 30.2%.

Craiului Forest bioarea holds 7.62% of the total length of the county's potable water distribution network, a slight decrease from 2014 when it was 7.72%. Additionally, the growth rate in the analyzed area is significantly lower than the county-wide trend (43.4% compared to 145.3%) (Table 16).

Table 16. Total Length of the Simple Potable Water Distribution Network, 2014 and 2023 (km, %)

	Kilometers	Kilometers	Dynamics (%)	Structure, 2023 (%)
	2014	2023		
Budureasa	23.3	25.5	9.4	9.13
Căbești	36	25	-30.6	8.95
Curățele	29.7	30.2	1.7	10.82
Dobrești	1.5	74.4	4,860.0	26.65
Pietroasa	20.3	20.3	0.0	7.27
Pomezueu	26.2	37.1	41.6	13.29
Răbăgani	40.7	40.7	0.0	14.58
Roșia	17	26	52.9	9.31
Total	190.8	280.8	43.4	100.00
Bihor County	2.521,9	3.664	145.3	
CF in total county	7.72	7.62		

Sources: own computation on NIS data.

The capacity of drinking water production facilities was, in 2023, 5,186 cubic meters/day, down -6% compared to 2014. In fact, three of the eight localities recorded decreases in drinking water production capacities (Pietroasa, Pomezueu and Răbăgani). In terms of structure, the largest share is held by Dobrești, with 21.1% of the total, followed by Pomezueu (19.8%) and Budureasa (16.2%). In fact, Dobrești increased its drinking water production capacity by 37%, followed by Căbești by 19.5%.

Reported at county level, CF represents 1.87% of the capacity of drinking water production facilities, while the decline dynamics is close to the county level.

The total quantity of water distributed in the CF mountain area was 1,007 thousand m.c. in 2023, an increase of 115.7% compared to 2014. The population's water consumption was, in 2023, 947 thousand m.c., representing 94.04% of total consumption and with an increase trend compared to 2014 of 132.11%. The highest consumption of distributed water is found in Dobrești (32.6%), followed by Pietroasa (14.1%) and Răbăgani. Regarding the quantity of water distributed to the population, the highest consumption is also found in Dobrești (34.53%), followed by Răbăgani (13.2%) and Pietroasa (12.25%) (table 16).

Reported at the level of Bihor County, the total distributed quantity in Craiului Forest was 4.27% of the quantity of water distributed, increasing compared to 2014 by 1.86 p. p.

In terms of household water consumption, CF holds 5.10% of the volume at the county level (increasing from 2.72% in 2014), with an even greater positive dynamic compared to the county (108.53 p.p.) (year 2023). The largest quantities of water distributed per inhabitant are recorded in Răbăgani (64.23 cubic meters/person), Dobrești (61.22 cubic meters/person) and Curățele (45.51%). Regarding the length of sewer pipes, this amounts to about 114.6 km in 2023, 31.9% higher than in 2020. Of the eight localities, only four have a sewer system, the rest being without. In terms of structure, most of the sewer network is located on the territory of Pomezueu commune (44.1%), followed by Dobrești (24.2%) and Răbăgani (22.8%). A spectacular increase in the sewer network in Dobrești locality, of 823.3%, is noted, but also a slight increase in Răbăgani (+31.9%). In Dobrești, a water treatment plant operates, which has a capacity of 345 cubic meters per day, representing 0.16% of the capacity of Bihor County.

There is no public transport in the upstream area, with no vehicles reported in the inventory for local public passenger transport. There are also no gas distribution pipelines.

Table 17 presents the SWOT analysis based on the analyzed indicators.

Table 17. SWOT Analysis – Utility infrastructure

STRONG POINTS	WEAK POINTS
<p>Increase in the drinking water distribution network. Dobrești increased its drinking water production capacity by 37%, followed by Căbești by 19.5%. The total amount of water distributed is increasing compared to 2014. The population's water consumption is on the rise. The highest consumption of distributed water is found in Dobrești (32.6%), followed by Pietroasa (14.1%) and Răbăgani. The amount of water distributed in the CF is 4.27% of the county, increasing compared to 2014 by 1.86 p.p. Household water consumption in the CF is 5.10% of the county (increasing from 2.72% in 2014), with an even higher positive dynamic compared to the county (108.53 p.p. p.) (2023). The length of the sewer pipes is increasing. In Dobrești, a water purification plant is operating.</p>	<p>The share of CF of 7.62% in the county, decreasing. The dynamics of CF is well below the growth trend recorded at the county level (43.4% compared to 145.3%). Reduction in the capacity of drinking water production facilities. Three of the eight localities recorded decreases in drinking water production capacities (Pietroasa, Pomezau and Răbăgani). Reported at the county level, CF represents 1.87% of the capacity of drinking water production facilities, while the dynamics of decrease is close to the county level. There is no thermal energy infrastructure. There is no public transport. There are no gas distribution pipelines.</p>
OPORTUNITIES	RISKS
<p>Programs financed from structural funds for financing local projects. Infrastructure projects financed through Resilience and Recovery National Plan. Better collaboration between UATs for the joint implementation of investments. Establishment of a public transport system between localities; Promotion of public-private partnerships. Use of modern gas, liquid fuel or biomass thermal power plants.</p>	<p>Loss of public infrastructure projects due to lack of co-financing. Low-income population. Increase in tariffs for various types of utilities. Deterioration of existing infrastructure. State monopoly for certain public utilities and public infrastructure. Installation of improvised central or local heating installations. Illegal felling of trees for firewood.</p>

Culture

In 2023, there were 15 libraries in operation in Craiului Forest, of which 5 were publicly owned (33.33%). In 2014, the number of libraries was 18, after which a decrease of 3 libraries was recorded (2 libraries in Dobrești and one in Pomezau). At the same time, the number of libraries remaining in public ownership was 6 (a public library in Pomezau commune was closed). The remaining 10 libraries are privately owned.

In Dobrești, the book collection is very valuable, almost entirely new, which, if placed closer to the beneficiaries, would be very popular with both students and teachers. The library was housed until recent years in the city hall on the first floor of the building. It is now temporarily moved to the same room as the archive. A next step would be to find a location near the school and the bus stop to be easily accessible to residents. Year of establishment 1990. It has its own headquarters. In 2009 the library is renovated, reorganized and following the competition for employment as a librarian it comes back to life in a new context.

In Căbești, the library was founded in 1954. The collection is reevaluated in 1966 and there is a fluctuation of responsibility, the library passing over the years from the tutelage of the city hall to the school and vice versa. Since 1990, the activity has resumed in the building of the cultural center, in two rooms. In 2012, investments and improvements began to be made in anticipation of the equipment from the Biblionet project, in the fifth series in 2013.

Table 18 presents the SWOT analysis based on the analyzed indicators.

Table 18. SWOT Analysis - Culture

STRONG POINTS	WEAK POINTS
Important cultural potential. Increasing the number of visitors.	Reduction in the number of libraries. Reduction in the number of volumes. Reduction in the number of readers. Reduction in the number of employees.
OPORTUNITIES	RISKS
Structural funds or government funds. Possibility of developing partnerships between institutions (local and foreign). Possibility of taking over and adapting good practice models from EU countries. Adapting the library book collection to new technologies RRPN – INVESTMENT I17. Funding schemes for libraries to become hubs for the development of digital skills – COMPONENT 7 Digital transformation.	Declining interest of the population in culture. Lack of interest of young people in maintaining local traditions and customs. Poor infrastructure to ensure the connection between different cultural objectives. Lack of involvement of those responsible in supporting the culture of the area.

CONCLUSIONS AND PROPOSALS ON THE INTEGRATED DEVELOPMENT OF THE *CRAIULUI FOREST MOUNTAIN AREA*

Following the analyses carried out during this study and, in particular, following the evaluation of all the strengths/weaknesses, opportunities/restrictions related to the territory of the *Craiului Forest mountain area*, the action plan and the strategy for the sustainable development of the complex and homogeneous mountain system will be developed.

The development objectives proposed and established for the CF bioarea must be consistent with the possible development alternatives, but also with those existing at the level of the eight component TAUs.

The development strategy for the CF bioarea must be built on the principles of sustainable development and aim to:

01. Ensure an appropriate framework that contributes to the creation of jobs (new and sustainable).

02. To promote a process oriented towards achieving common objectives and priorities, shared by the entire community.

03. To contribute to a better life for the citizens of the area.

The major development directions for the period 2021-2027 could target the following major areas of intervention:

The following major development directions (Table 19) for the area are proposed (programming period 2021-2027):

Table 19. Development directions

<i>MID 1. Development of mountain agriculture</i>	This direction aims to develop an agricultural sector by increasing the competitiveness of mountain products, with the help of innovative knowledge processes, by using modern techniques and forming systems that contribute to greater adaptability to current frequent and abrupt changes. Among the actions we can mention: supporting cooperation between farms and farmers, promoting agricultural investments and supporting activities for the certification of traditional products, promoting the identity of the mountain territory, increasing the profitability of mountain agricultural practices in order to increase the productivity of specific agricultural work.
<i>MID 2. Development of environmental infrastructure</i>	Environmental problems affect mountainous areas, therefore, a field of intervention is proposed to protect nature. The strategic field aims to promote projects that support the increase in the quality of the infrastructure necessary for environmental protection (modernization/expansion of roads and access roads, utility networks, public lighting, household and industrial waste collection, protection of communities from natural risks, etc.). The territory lends itself to a sustainable use of renewable energy sources, this being an advantage in ensuring a quality living environment.
<i>MID 3. Supporting the business environment and the local economy</i>	The aim is to develop the local economy by ensuring a prosperous and healthy business environment, built on competition and supporting the real demands of the market. Particular attention must be paid to attracting the necessary financing resources for local infrastructure investments that support economic development and the creation of an attractive general framework. In the mountainous area of the PC, as shown by the analyses carried out, the service sector holds a special place (trade, transport, tourism, etc.), which can be a real engine of local economic development.
<i>MID 4. Supporting and promoting mountain tourism</i>	The intervention must aim to protect the natural, cultural and historical heritage, along with a sustainable valorization of the tourist heritage, through the sustainable valorization of resources, the development of accommodation and leisure services and infrastructure, as well as activities to promote the tourist potential of the area. Investments in accommodation structures, eco-tourism and agro-tourism will be supported.
<i>MID 5. Culture, education and sports activities</i>	The aim is to increase the attractiveness of the mountain area for its inhabitants, especially for young people, by supporting activities related to education, culture and sports, adapted to the target groups. An emphasis will be placed on the need to capitalize on the existing material base and on stimulating the involvement of all those interested in the educational process, training and transmitting traditional practices to future generations, examples of good practice, elements of local tradition, etc. Indirectly, a reduction in the risk of school dropout and the crime rate among young people can be achieved, as well as a rejuvenation of the area.
<i>MID 6. Development of local human resources and the social sector</i>	Human resources are strategic in supporting the development of the mountain area. Thus, measures can be taken to promote vocational training in key areas of the local economy, to connect lifelong learning with the needs identified on the labor market, by increasing the quality of life of disadvantaged/marginalized or vulnerable people, by implementing projects in an efficient public administration-civil society partnership framework that will bring added value to the lives of citizens in the mountain area.
<i>MID 7. Developing the administrative and organizational capacity of local authorities</i>	By strengthening the administrative and institutional capacity of the public administration in the eight ATUs, the following actions can be taken: strengthening efficient decision-making processes, accountability processes that improve organizational effectiveness, improving the quality and efficiency of standards in the provision of public services, as well as increasing the absorption of structural and cohesion funds in the Pădurea Craiului area

This article aims to provide stakeholders (public, local or central authorities, researchers, academic and university environments, etc.) with a synthetic, theoretical and practical presentation of a model for the analysis and strategic planning of a homogeneous mountain territory. The study thus proposes and tests the development of a spatial analysis based on indicators, on the identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT), for a homogeneous territorial system, with multiple and exceptional values, such as Pădurea Craiului.

As a result, the areas of intervention and actions identified in the article support the subsequent decision-making phase, coordinated and managed by the local authorities involved. The innovative value of the research comes not only from the integrated methodological approach based on the combination of spatial analysis, indicator systems and traditional SWOT analysis, but also from the contextual characteristics of the investigated area. Moreover, the integrated and innovative framework proposed in the article also has general applicability, due to the possibility of replicating the research strategy and methodological approach in other specific contexts of mountain areas.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data supporting the conclusions of this study are available in official statistics, on the website of the National Institute of Statistics and Eurostat.

REFERENCES

- Antonescu D.** 2024. *Planificarea teritorială integrată a unui sistem montan complex. Microregiunea Bazinul Dornelor*, Lumen: Lumen Publishing House, Iași, România, ISBN: 978-973-166-634-1, <https://edituralumen.ro/planificarea-teritoriala-integrata-a-unui-sistem-montan-complex-microregiunea-bazinul-dornelor-daniela-antonescu/>
- Antonescu D, Popa F.** 2014. Dezvoltarea regională și planificarea teritorială în contextul noii politici de coeziune (2014-2020) [Regional development and territorial programming in context of new cohesion policy (2014-2020)]," MPRA Paper 54202, University Library of Munich, Germany. Available online: <https://ideas.repec.org/p/pramprapa/54202.html> [Accessed 27 January 2025].
- European Commission.** 2021. Territorial Agenda 2030, European Commission, Brussels, Belgium.
- Goran C.** 1981. *Catalogul sistematic al peșterilor din România*. Editura Consiliului Național pentru Educație Fizică și Sport, București, România, 496 pp.
- Rusu T.** 1988. *Pe Urmele Apelor Subterane. Carstul din Munții Pădurea Craiului*, Editura Dacia, Cluj-Napoca.
- Alexandrescu-Dersca M.M, Bulgaru V.** 1972. *A. D. Xenopol și continuitatea poporului român în Dacia pe baza permanenței îndeletnicirilor sale agricole*, Editura Academiei Republicii Socialiste România.
- Ianoș I.** 2001. *Sisteme teritoriale*, Ed. Tehnică, București, România.
- Ciangă N, Deszi St.** 2007. *Amenajare Turistică*, Presa Universitară Clujeană, Cluj -Napoca, România.

- Surd V**, coord. 2005, *Amenajarea teritoriului și infrastructuri tehnice*, Editura. Presa Universitară Clujeană, Cluj –Napoca, România.
- Cândea M, Bran F, Cimpoeu I**. 2006. *Organizarea, amenajarea și dezvoltarea durabilă a spațiului geografic*, Editura Universitară, București.
- Puşcaşu V**. 2005. *Planificarea sistemelor teritoriale*, Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, București, România.
- Tălângă C**. 2015. *Planificare teritorială strategică*. Editura Universitară, București, România, ISBN 978-606-28-0365-0.
- Zotic V**. 2005. *Componentele operaționale ale organizării spațiului geografic*, Presa Clujeană, Cluj, România.
- United Nations Human Settlements Programme (UN-Habitat)** (2015). International Guidelines on Urban and Territorial Planning, United Nations Human Settlements Programme, HS Number: HS/059/15E. https://unhabitat.org/sites/default/files/download-manager-files/IG-UTP_English.pdf
- Peștera din Sohodol Munții Pădurea Craiului**, Available online: <https://www.speologie.org/peștera-din-sohodol>, [Accessed 28 January 2025].
- Peștera Vadu Crișului**. Available online: <https://padureacraiului.ro/peștera-vadu-crisului/> [Accessed 29 January 2025].
- Peștera de la Astileu**, Available online: <https://www.speologie.org/peștera-de-la-astileu> [Accessed 29 January 2025].
- Centrul pentru Arii Protejate și Dezvoltare Durabilă**, Available online: <https://www.capdd-bihor.org/> [Accessed 29 January 2025].
- Fișa sitului Natura 2000 ROSPA0115 Defileul Crișului – Valea Iadului** [Accessed 29 January 2025].
- Management Plan of Pădurea Craiului**, Available on: <https://www.capdd-bihor.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/Conceptul-planului-de-management-pentru-situl-Natura-2000.pdf> [Accessed 29 January 2025].
- <https://www.wall-street.ro/articol/Economie/178434/romania-ultimul-loc-din-ue-in- ceea-ce-priveste-densitate-de-imm-uri.html>
- <https://bibliotecibihorene.blogspot.com/2023/01/dobresti-si-pocola.html>